

“A search for female specimens of an undescribed spider species in the genus *Tiso*”

Final report submitted by:

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Abstract:

Hand and sweep net collecting and curation spiders from Ram Pasture and Squam Swamp occurred from July 29th to August 9th, 2019 to attempt to add female (and additional male) specimens of a yet-to-be described spider believed to be in the genus *Tiso* (Linyphiidae). The genus, first described by Simon (Simon, 1884) currently has 7 described members (van Helsdingen, 2015). Intermittent sampling by prior arachnologists (Draney and McKenna-Foster pers. comm.), and by the author, yielded 5 males of this undescribed species on Nantucket Island (from Ram Pasture and Squam Swamp) from 2015-2017. Spiders of this genus are small (1.6 mm to 2.2 mm in length), males have slightly raised eye regions, and rather small eyes relative to other members of the Linyphiidae. Abdomen coloration is usually black to brownish-grey with yellow tinged legs. The genus is most commonly collected in Scandinavian countries, with two species, *Tiso aestivus* and *Tiso vagans*, being found in North America. Sampling of the above natural areas on Nantucket generated 0 new specimens that could be used for the description of the species this past season. All bi-catch spiders that were collected were identified, with voucher specimens of new “island list” species deposited in the Maria Mitchell collection, and other specimens housed at the UMASS Boston Field Station in their teaching collection.

Introduction:

The Order Araneae currently houses over 41,000 described species, with 400-500 new species being added yearly (Kuntner and Coddington, 2009). Rarely is a new spider species found in

one of the larger bodied families, such as the Theraphosidae. When a new species is added in the Theraphosidae, it makes the “world news” circles (Midgley and Englebret, 2019). Most commonly, new species in the Araneae come from large sampling studies (Dobyns, 1996) that yield small and/or cryptic spider species, new to science. As Nantucket Island has a wonderful history of being sampled by professional arachnologists, collections from early giants in the field, like J. H. Emerton (1891), to more recent arachnolophiles like Andrew McKenna-Foster (formerly of Maria Mitchell), Michael Draney (University of Wisconsin Green Bay), and the author, have generated a robust catalogue of island “dwelling” species. This allows for quick confirmation of not only new species for the island list maintained at Maria Mitchell, but aids in helping researchers and students determine if they might have a specimen that is new to science altogether.

In 2016, the author, and the UMASS of Boston ENVSTY “Spiders of Nantucket” class, collected an unidentifiable male spider in the Family Linyphiidae in August sampling. Discussions with Dr. Michael Draney (UW Green Bay) and Mr. Andrew McKenna-Foster revealed that they too had specimens that matched the male collected in 2016. In order for the triumvirate to forge ahead with a proper species description, it was agreed that the next time any of us were able, we would look to add a female member of this group. While descriptions of species using only one of the sexes is possible (Dobyns and Bond, 1996 and Merrett P. & Stevens R.A., 1999), it is a practice that is generally frowned upon. The purpose of seeking the NBI grant was to assist with travel related expenses, and place the author on-island prior to the teaching the ENVSTY 321 course so sampling could begin in the natural areas adult male specimens of the species had been collected from in the past (Draney and McKenna-Foster pers. comm.).

Methods:

The primary investigator (July 29th and 30th), and 8 students from the UMASS Boston ENVSTY 321 course taught at the UMASS Boston Field Station collected (August 1st to August 8th) in Ram Pasture and Sanford Farm areas, as well as Squam Swamp, with sweep nets, and hand

collecting techniques (aspirators and “picking”) to survey the small linyphiid spider populations of the properties intermittently from the 29th of July to the 9th of August 2018.

Collecting was done during the post-sunrise morning hours, as well as early afternoon hours, until collector fatigue set in.

All collected spiders were identified to the species level, and then curated and added to either the UMass of Boston collection, or housed within the Maria Mitchell Association collection.

Results:

Island sampling over the study period yielded 202 adult spider specimens in 17 families. There were 11 unique genera identified, with 13 species collected in the target family, Linyphiidae. No additional specimens of the undescribed species of *Tiso* were captured.

Discussion:

The collection, and identification, of small, cryptic spiders of the Family Linyphiidae is never an easy task. While publications on the phenology of adulthood in the Genus *Tiso* are scarce (Locket, Millidge and Merrett, 1974), European records have shown July through September as a common timeframe for *Tiso* specimens to be mature at collection. As past sampling in July and August on Nantucket Island had yielded adult males of this species, the timing of this round of sampling (late July to August 9th) for the female specimens seemed to make sense. Anytime an investigator is searching an island that has 105 square miles of diverse habitats, looking for a 1.6-2.2 mm in length rare and cryptic species, the likelihood of success is small. The failure to add a female to the collections of this yet to be described species was not a loss, as the spider species list generated from the collection added several new species (in and out of the Family Linyphiidae) to the island list. Additionally, the collection and identification of *Micaria emertoni* (Gnaphosidae), which is a new addition to the Maria Mitchell list published on their

website, allowed for my students to delve into the long and rich history of arachnology on the island via the spiders namesake (Emerton).

While last year's sampling does not allow for a species description to be published for this potential new member of the Genus *Tiso*, it does spur on the desire for more collecting efforts to this end. And, with a set of males specimens in-hand, the description process will begin to form up in the coming year.

Acknowledgements:

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Without the facilities of UMASS Boston at our disposal, no identifications would be possible! To this end, I would like to acknowledge Dr. Alan Christian as my point of contact with UMASS Boston, and the driver of this course (and therefore the person responsible for me being on island to collect males in the first place).

Additionally, many thanks to the past and current Directors of Maria Mitchell for opening their doors and specimens to my students and to me. The wealth of arachnological information housed in their collection is spectacular, and access to these over our visits through the years has been greatly appreciated!

Last, but not least, I would like to recognize the Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative research program for the small grant I received. The help you provided got me to the island, an island I have fallen in love with over the last 6 years. And, in this day and age of diminishing funds for

more “naturalist” like pursuits in biological sciences, I am humbled to have been assisted in my passion for spider identification by the organization. Many thanks!

Literature Cited:

Dobyns, J. (1996) Effects of Sampling Intensity on the Collection of Spider (Araneae) Species and the Estimation of Species Richness, *Environmental Entomology*, Volume 26, Issue 2, 1 April 1997, Pages 150–162.

Dobyns J, Bond J. (1996) A New Species of *Theridion* from Northeastern Georgia (Araneae, Theridiidae). *Journal of Arachnology* 24:89-92.

Emerton J. H. (1891) New England Spiders of the Family Attidae. *Transactions of the Connecticut Academy of Science* VIII (XIV): 220-252, plates XVI-XXI.

Kuntner M, Coddington JA (2009) Discovery of the Largest Orbweaving Spider Species: The Evolution of Gigantism in *Nephila*. *PLOS ONE* 4(10): e7516.

Merrett P. & Stevens R.A. (1999) The male of *Nothopantes horridus* Merrett & Stevens (Araneae: Linyphiidae). *Bull. Br. arachnol. Soc.* 11 (4): 129-130.

Locket, Millidge & Merritt (1974) British Spiders, Vols I - III
ISBN-13 978-1-904690-15-3

Midgley JM, Engelbrecht I (2019) New collection records for Theraphosidae (Araneae, Mygalomorphae) in Angola, with the description of a remarkable new species of *Ceratogyrus*. *African Invertebrates* 60(1): 1-13.

Simon, E. (1884) *Les arachnides de France. Tome cinquième, deuxième et troisième partie.* Roret, Paris, 180-185.

Helsdingen, P.J. van (2015) *Catalogus van de Nederlandse spinnen. Versie 2015.1. Laatst bijgewerkt: 1 mei 2015*